

Munir's Cobweb of Mental Health

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Mental health challenges are like a labyrinthine maze- tangled cobwebs. Once it attaches to someone, it never leaves—though it rests upon the individual to either embrace it and become resilient, or face consistent turmoil.

Individuals facing mental health challenges due to man-made disasters (such as mass shootings or terrorism), natural disasters (such as climate change, epidemic, endemic, etc), or personal experiences or circumstances (such as domestic violence), often find themselves in snarled situations that impede their ability to navigate and access sustainable solutions.

Munir expressed, “A person facing mental health challenges can be metaphorically likened to a pendulum- oscillations and swings (fluctuations in mood and motivation; depressive episodes, etc). If left unaddressed, this cycle of negative thoughts and emotional setbacks may lead to isolation or incline individuals towards violence. If addressed but then relapsed after some time, a person may become numb to their feelings, thoughts, and emotions.”

Munir further stated, “We are aware of our struggles, and we have the power to choose whether to narrate them with others or not. The human mind is inherently unpredictable. We live in a society where sharing is considered shameful. At times, some individuals choose to express their vulnerabilities to others, and that is acceptable. On the other hand, some prefer to keep their struggles to themselves. It is fine as long as doing so does not cause unrest or inner turmoil.”

While counselors and psychologists can offer valuable assistance, it is important to acknowledge that their approaches may inadvertently lead to the temporary suppression of emotions or provide short-term relief.

Munir's cobweb of mental health focuses on understanding the actual cause of mental health challenges through reflective practice. The philosophy behind this approach is that individuals should be equipped with self-help skills such as self-awareness, self-care, self-acceptance, storytelling, emotional expression and navigation, resilience, empathy, openness, stress management, and networking since childhood (ladder approach- simplicity to complexity) to understand and manage their experiences. While others can offer pastoral support, true recovery and restoration of mental health can only come from within.

Munir expressed, "We've all heard the rumors about how ABC died, but the truth is buried with them. We can only speculate and puzzle over the possibilities."

Give individuals time to heal, and respect their personal space. Understand that they may display various behaviors, such as silence, appearing delusional, or violent. Avoid being judgmental and assure them of your support. However, maintain a level of observation and vigilance for their safety without overwhelming them during their vulnerable state.

By developing a deeper understanding of personal experiences and taking proactive steps to address mental health, individuals can take control of their well-being for a brighter and more fulfilling future.